

IS THE FORMATION OF “BLACK HOLES” POSSIBLE WITHOUT COLLAPSE?

Adilova Xalida Shamshetdin qizi

2nd year of master's degree Karakalpakstan State University

+998973541400

xalida-2015@mail.ru

Abstract: The aim of the article is to attempt to explain certain moments in the mechanism of the emergence and evolution of “black holes”. In particular, the question of the formation of supermassive "black holes" is considered and an assumption is made as to why they are necessarily located in the center of galaxies.

Key words: «Black hole»; space; Universe; galaxy

1. Introduction

In the eighteenth century, I. Newton came to the conclusion about the corpuscular nature of light. Based on this idea, as well as the law of gravity, the Englishman D. Michell, back in 1784, was the first in the world to express a logical and sound idea about the possibility of the existence of peculiar objects in outer space, which are now known to us as "black holes" [1].

Currently, their existence has been convincingly proven, albeit indirectly. It seems that the word "indirect" should not confuse anyone, because many data and facts are obtained in this way. No one, for example, has directly taken a sample from an intergalactic gas cloud, weighed the Sun on a scale, measured the diameter of an atom with a ruler, etc., but this does not give reason to doubt most of these facts.

2. Relevance

For modern science, “black holes” are still by and large mysterious objects. Although a consensus has been reached in the scientific community on the continuity

of the mass spectrum of these objects from microscopic values to supermassive, the mechanism of their formation and evolution raises many questions, especially for objects located at the extreme limits of their mass range. Getting answers to these questions is of vital importance for understanding the nature of the universe as a whole.

3. Purpose

The purpose of this article is an attempt to explain individual moments in the mechanism of the emergence and evolution of "black holes".

4. Scientific novelty

If we consider a "black hole" as a state of extreme deformation of a local region of the Universe's space, then first of all we need to understand what causes can cause such a state.

Obviously, in accordance with the General Theory of Relativity (GRT), in order to achieve such a degree of deformation of space, a colossal amount of matter must be concentrated in its limited area. Theoretically, the possible mechanism of such concentration is well developed, and simplistically it includes a chain of the following events:

gravitational compression of a cloud of gas (hydrogen) to such an extent that a thermonuclear reaction occurs in it, i.e. a star is formed and lights up;

thermal radiation of the thermonuclear reaction stops further gravitational compression;

in the process of hydrogen burning, new elements are formed, up to iron;

after the hydrogen is produced, the thermonuclear reaction stops, and its thermal radiation ceases to restrain gravitational compression;

there is a gravitational collapse of the star.

Depending on the initial mass, the star can turn into a white dwarf, a neutron star or a "black hole". Theoretical conditions for the transformation of a star into a white dwarf or a neutron star have been established "The Chandrasekhar Limit" [2] and the "Oppenheimer-Volkov Limit" [3]. For a white dwarf, this is the mass of the

original star in the range of 1.38...1.44 Solar masses, for a neutron star of the order of 2...3.

The mass (as well as the conditions) under which the final state of the evolution of a star is a black hole is not precisely defined, but it is assumed that it should be greater than the values given above.

Such a mechanism for the appearance of "black holes" seems to be quite real and perhaps there is a large and diverse number of these objects in the Universe, formed in this way. However, there remains the question of the emergence of both microscopic "black holes" and supermassive ones. And if the first of them have not yet been discovered, and in general, they do not attract much attention to themselves at the moment because of their presumably insignificant (?) The same cannot be said about supermassive rotating "black holes" located in the centers of the vast majority of galaxies.

The fact that such a location is not random and it plays a very important role in the life of the galaxy, in my opinion, is obvious and this will be discussed below. It also seems very doubtful that supermassive "black holes" could grow to such a size in a fairly limited time from relatively small "black holes" formed from collapsed stars. These doubts were especially reinforced by the discovery of young supermassive "black holes" whose age does not exceed one billion years.

An attempt to answer this question by assuming the possibility of a direct collapse of a hydrogen cloud into a "black hole" (without intermediate stages, such as a long period of star formation and an even longer process of hydrogen burning in it) seems unsatisfactory. It is quite obvious that during gravitational compression in hydrogen, when it reaches a metallic state (which of course is a very high density, but far from the one necessary for the formation of a "black hole"), a thermonuclear reaction will begin, the thermal radiation of which will definitely prevent further compression of the hydrogen cloud to the required density.

Such a collapse can take place if the cluster (cloud) consists of other elements (not hydrogen). In this case, the gravitational compression will not be interrupted halfway due to the start of a thermonuclear reaction. However, this option seems unlikely, since it can be realized only when the remnants from the explosions of stars can somehow randomly gather into a sufficiently large cluster. Again, for this option, it is necessary to go through long stages of star formation and hydrogen burning in them in order to synthesize these other elements. Therefore, it is also impossible to explain to them the possibility of the formation of young supermassive "black holes".

Probably, it is worth mentioning here another possible option of a direct collapse. If we assume the existence of "dark matter", then with a fair share of fantasy, we can imagine the formation of "black holes" from this collapsed mythical substance. Moreover, any properties can be attributed to this substance in order to justify the possibility of such a collapse. Although, perhaps, it is not necessary to completely reject the prospect of such an option, which theoretically can be realized at any time, even, for example, before the formation of baryonic matter. However, in my opinion, the probability of this is small, even compared to the previous option.

There is also an assumption that a supermassive "black hole" could have formed from a preceding "white hole". In my opinion, this assumption is interesting, since theoretically the possibility of the existence of "white holes" follows from the Schwarzschild solution of the GRT equations. However, I will not consider it here, since there are no observational confirmations of the presence of such objects in outer space to date, whereas, for example, there are many of them for "black holes". In addition, in this case, the question also remains, but how could such a supermassive "white hole" be formed in turn?

It can be seen from the above that there are significant difficulties in understanding the mechanism of occurrence of both supermassive "black holes" and the features of their location in galaxies, as well as small (up to the size of atoms) objects of this kind.

However, if we assume that space has some kind of physical essence, then it becomes possible to answer these questions. I will make a reservation right away that I fully agree that such an assumption is so far only hypothetical. However, a number of experimental and observational facts are difficult to interpret otherwise than as support for such a version. Confirmation of the theoretically predicted Lense-Thirring effect of "twisting" space around rotating bodies [4] and [5], as well as proof of the existence of gravitational waves [6], which can propagate only in the fabric of space-time, show the vulnerability and not indisputability of the representation of space only in the form of mathematical abstraction.

Therefore, based on the assumption of the physical essence of space, I will formulate the scientific novelty as follows: the state of extreme deformation of the local region of the Universe space (that is, a "black hole") can be achieved not only due to a high concentration of matter in it with its subsequent collapse, but also have a natural origin. Natural origin here means that during the formation and expansion of space in it, the probability of occurrence and deepening of various topological distortions (defects) is not excluded, some of which may reach a state of extreme deformation. And only natural (primary) "black holes", regardless of their origin (due to topological defects in space or as a result of the collapse of "dark matter", as well as possibly other, as yet unknown reasons) have a chance to grow to gigantic sizes. "Black holes" formed from collapsed stars (that is, during a period of time when the universe has already become partially structured) have practically no such possibility.

5. Results

The proposed hypothesis makes it possible to explain the possibility of the existence in the Universe of a continuous spectrum of masses of "black holes", ranging from microscopic objects to supermassive ones. Of particular interest is the probable course of evolution of primary (natural) "black holes" to supermassive "black holes" located in the centers of galaxies.

The course of reasoning may be as follows. In the process of the emergence and expansion of space, a topological defect with a state of extreme deformation, a kind of “gravitational pit” or a primary "black hole" could form in it. This defect could have formed at any stage, including long before the appearance of the baryonic substance. In the latter case, the primary "black hole" could probably begin to fill with the components of the primary plasma, radiation, and, assuming the existence of the "dark mother", also its particles.

By the time the formation of baryonic matter began, the primary "black hole" in question may have already been able to represent a region of sufficiently high gravitational attraction, where the emerging baryonic matter was rushing. That is, two interrelated processes developed – a further increase in the mass of the primary "black hole", mainly due to the absorption of baryonic matter, and the concentration around it, as a center of attraction, of large masses of this matter, from which the galaxy was subsequently formed. The last phrase is actually a description of the modern idea of a quasar - a small region in the center of the galaxy, located around a huge "black hole" and filled with matter that has not yet entered the stage of star formation.

From this example, the determining role of the growing primary "black hole" on the process of galaxy formation is clearly visible, as well as why it occupies a central place in it and why the “building material” and the time of growth of its mass to supermassive values is quite sufficient. Also, in my opinion, it is obvious that "black holes" formed from collapsed stars do not have the opportunity to grow to supermassive in a reasonable time, and are generally unable to occupy a place in the center of galaxies. I.e. a supermassive "black hole” could have developed exclusively from the primary, which actually formed the galaxy, taking a central place in it.

Perhaps it is worth explaining the categoricity of the last statement here. Obviously, the gigantic number of galaxies in the observable Universe (according to the latest data, more than a trillion) implies a variety of their shapes, masses,

properties, etc. Probably not all of them have a supermassive "black hole" in the center. It may well be that in a local region of space having a topological defect that causes increased gravitational attraction, however, there were no areas with a state of extreme deformation, i.e. primary "black holes". This, in general, will not prevent matter from "flowing" into this region and forming a galaxy, but there will be no "black hole" in its center.

And even if, in the future, one of the central stars of such a galaxy turns into a "black hole" as a result of collapse, it will not have the opportunity to grow to a supermassive one. There will be no necessary "building" material around it, since all the matter has already been distributed among the stars, and a young and small "black hole" will not have enough gravitational forces to attract and absorb them. If, for clarity, we imagine the stars in the form of tennis balls (with a diameter of ~ 40 mm), then on this scale the distance between these balls will be on average more than 1000 km of almost empty space. Even in dense star clusters, this distance will be about 100 km. Therefore, rare comets, random asteroids and some remnants of interstellar gas - that's the whole meager "diet" of the newly formed "black hole". So it is not necessary to count on the fact that the "black hole" in question, even being in a dense star cluster, will be able to grow to supermassive, absorbing several million solar masses (not to mention tens of millions or billions), or merging with similar small "black holes". Of course, theoretically it can be assumed that in multiple cases of merging of similar galaxies (without supermassive "black holes" in the center), in the end the "winner" will have a supermassive "black hole", but the probability of this, in my opinion, differs little from zero.

I will assume that only in the conditions of the early Universe, when the process of formation of a large amount of baryonic matter was rapidly proceeding, all the prerequisites were created for the rapid growth of primary "black holes" to gigantic sizes due to the intensive absorption of such accessible and "nobody's" matter. If by this time the "black hole" already had sufficient gravitational attraction, then it should not be surprising that, for example, the mass is quite young (less than 4 billion

years old) The "black hole" (quasar TON 618) exceeds 66 billion solar masses. Probably, this had a direct impact on the size of the galaxy formed by it.

It seems to be expected that the incredible mass of "black holes" will be increasingly detected at distances correlated with the period of the early Universe, since subsequently there were no such favorable conditions for their growth. Therefore, the development of "black holes" in the subsequent stages of the life of the Universe is mainly limited to much smaller sizes, of the order of Sgr A, as in the Milky Way. Naturally, not every primary "black hole" will be able to grow to supermassive or even to any noticeable. I assume that the vast majority of them remain very small, since due to random reasons and the possible heterogeneity of space [7], priority directions of "runoff" of matter are created not to all, but only to some primary "black holes".

6. Conclusions

The assumption of the physical essence of space and the representation of a "black hole" in the form of a state of extreme deformation of a local region of the Universe space allows us to explain the possibility of the emergence and evolution of these objects in the entire spectrum of their masses.

If the properties of the supposed physical essence of space are not subject to stress relaxation and thixotropy (time factor), then hypothetical evaporation by Hawking radiation [8] of the mass of the "black hole" even to zero will not lead to its complete destruction.

7. Conclusion

The proposed hypothesis allows us to answer a number of topical and problematic questions of the origin and evolution of "black holes". However, it is based on the assumption of the still hypothetical physical essence of space. There are data in favor of this assumption, but they are currently insufficient for a reliable assessment of the assumed physical properties.

However, I hope that now the study of gravity and space has accelerated and has become a priority for a number of leading countries. It is possible that significant

funding invested in the creation of means of observing outer space and in the study of its properties (projects such as LIGO, etc.) can lead to breakthrough discoveries in this area in the near future.

Bibliographic list:

1. The black hole. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Черная_дыра (accessed: 04/25/2021);
2. The Chandrasekhar limit. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Limit_cHandrasekara (accessed: 04/23/2021);
3. Oppenheimer-Volkov limit. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Limit_Oppenheimer-_volkov (accessed: 04/23/2021);
4. C. W. F. Everitt et al. Gravity Probe B: Final results of a space experiment to test general relativity, *Physical Review Letters* (May 1, 2011);
5. Ciufolini, I.; A. Paolozzi, E. C. Pavlis, J. C. Ries, R. Koenig, R. Matzner, A. Sindoni G. and H. Neumayer Gravitomagnetism and Its Measurement with Laser Ranging to the LAGEOS Satellites and a GRACE Earth Gravity Models // *General Relativity and John Archibald Wheeler* (eng.). — SpringerLink, 2010. — Vol. 367. — P. 371-434. — (Astrophysics and Space Science Library);
6. B. P. Abbott (LIGO Scientific Collaboration and Virgo Collaboration) et al. Observation of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Black Hole Merger // *Physical Review Letters* : journal. — 2016. — Vol. 116, no. 6;
7. Koshkin. Yu.A. The inhomogeneity of the relic radiation indicates the inhomogeneity of space? [Electronic resource] // *SCI-ARTICLE.RU* . - 2021. URL: <https://sci-article.ru/stat.php?i=1617459520>;
8. Hawking radiation. [Electronic resource] // URL: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Излучение_Хокинга (accessed: 04/23/2021).